

METHODS USED IN TEACHING ENGLISH TO STUDENTS

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Abstract

The methods used in teaching English to students have evolved significantly over time, reflecting changes in educational theories, technological advancements, and shifts in pedagogical priorities. Early approaches, such as the Grammar-Translation Method and the Direct Method, emphasized rote memorization and direct immersion in the target language. Later methods, like the Audio-Lingual Method, focused on repetitive drills and language patterns, while Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) emerged as a response to emphasize real-world communication, fluency, and interaction over strict grammatical accuracy. More recent approaches, such as Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT) and Content and Language Integrated Learning (CLIL), integrate language learning with practical tasks and subject content, fostering a more dynamic, student-centered environment. Other methods, like the Silent Way and Total Physical Response (TPR), prioritize learner autonomy and kinesthetic learning, offering diverse pathways for engaging students in the language acquisition process. The choice of method depends on the learners' needs, context, and learning objectives, with many educators blending approaches to create a balanced, effective curriculum. This diversity in teaching methods highlights the complexity of language education and the importance of adapting strategies to ensure learners' comprehensive language development.

Key words: Communicative Language Teaching (CLT), Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT), Grammar-Translation Method, Direct Method, Audiolingual Method, Total Physical Response (TPR), Content-Based Instruction (CBI), Content and Language Integrated Learning (CLIL), Lexical Approach, Project-Based Learning (PBL), Flipped Classroom, Blended Learning.

The approaches can be broadly categorized into traditional methods, communicative approaches, and modern methods, each with its own strengths and objectives.

1. Grammar-Translation Method (GTM)

Overview: One of the oldest methods, focused primarily on grammar rules, vocabulary, and translation between the native language and English.

Focus: Grammar rules, memorization, translation, and reading comprehension.

Characteristics:

Lessons are taught in the students' native language.

Focus on written language rather than spoken skills.

Emphasis on rote memorization of vocabulary and grammar rules.

Pros: Works well for learners who need to master formal language, especially for academic or reading comprehension.

Cons: Limited focus on speaking and listening; not communicative.

2. Direct Method (Natural Method)

Overview: Focuses on teaching English directly through immersion, without using the learner's native language.

Focus: Speaking and listening skills, vocabulary, pronunciation.

Characteristics:

Grammar is taught inductively (i.e., students learn rules through usage, not explanation).

Only English is used during instruction.

Emphasis on everyday vocabulary and practical sentences.

Pros: Helps students develop natural language skills and confidence in speaking.

Cons: May be difficult for beginners, as there is no translation or explanation in the native language.

3. Audio-Lingual Method

Overview: Based on behaviorist theories of learning, focusing on repetitive drills and practice to develop automatic language responses.

Focus: Speaking and listening, sentence structures, pronunciation.

Characteristics:

Heavy use of repetition and pattern drills (e.g., fill-in-the-blank exercises, substitution drills).

Error correction is immediate to reinforce correct language patterns.

Little to no focus on writing or reading at first stages.

Pros: Good for developing fluency and helping students acquire correct pronunciation.

Cons: Can be monotonous and doesn't always promote critical thinking or creativity.

4. Communicative Language Teaching (CLT)

Overview: This is one of the most popular and modern methods. The focus is on communication rather than strict grammar rules.

Focus: Speaking, listening, and communicative competence.

Characteristics:

Emphasis on real-world communication and authentic materials.

Lessons are centered around tasks (e.g., role plays, problem-solving).

Focus on fluency over accuracy; learners are encouraged to speak, even if their grammar isn't perfect.

Pros: Builds confidence and real-world communication skills, adaptable to various contexts.

Cons: Some grammar may be overlooked, and not all students may feel comfortable in spontaneous speaking situations.

5. Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT)

Overview: Focuses on using tasks as the central unit of instruction. Tasks are activities with clear outcomes that use language in a real-world context.

Focus: Problem-solving, interaction, and practical communication.

Characteristics:

Students complete meaningful tasks (e.g., planning a trip, making a presentation, writing a report) using English.

Grammar and vocabulary are learned through the tasks, rather than isolated instruction.

Emphasis on process and outcome.

Pros: Encourages practical language use, promotes active learning, and prepares students for real-life situations.

Cons: May be challenging for beginners, and some students may feel overwhelmed by the lack of explicit grammar instruction.

6. Content and Language Integrated Learning (CLIL)

Overview: This approach integrates subject content (like science, history, or math) with language learning. It is used primarily in bilingual education or in English as a medium of instruction.

Focus: Content mastery through the English language.

Characteristics:

Language learning is tied to other subjects (e.g., students learn science vocabulary while studying biology in English).

Focus on both academic content and language skills simultaneously.

Typically used in immersion settings or bilingual programs.

Pros: Students gain both subject knowledge and language proficiency.

Cons: Can be complex for students without a strong foundation in the language.

7. The Silent Way

Overview: A highly student-centered approach where the teacher speaks minimally and students are encouraged to discover the language for themselves.

Focus: Pronunciation, structure, and self-discovery of language rules.

Characteristics:

The teacher uses gestures, colored rods, and visuals to prompt student learning.

Students are encouraged to experiment with language and take risks.

Teachers correct errors only when necessary, encouraging independent problem-solving.

Pros: Promotes learner autonomy and critical thinking.

Cons: Can feel uncomfortable for students who are used to more structured instruction; may be difficult for beginners.

8. Lexical Approach

Overview: Focuses on teaching vocabulary and fixed word combinations (collocations, phrases) rather than isolated grammar rules.

Focus: Vocabulary acquisition and understanding language patterns.

Characteristics:

Emphasizes learning chunks of language (e.g., "make a decision," "in the meantime").

Vocabulary is taught in context rather than as isolated lists.

Grammar is viewed as the way words combine to form meaning, not as a set of rules.

Pros: Helps learners sound more natural and fluent in English.

Cons: May neglect deeper grammar understanding and abstract structures.

9. Total Physical Response (TPR)

Overview: A language teaching method that integrates physical movement with language learning. It's especially useful for beginners and younger learners.

Focus: Listening and comprehension.

Characteristics:

The teacher gives commands (e.g., "stand up," "sit down"), and students respond physically.

Focus on comprehension and vocabulary development.

Students are not required to speak until they are comfortable.

Pros: Helps students learn in a natural, stress-free way; effective for kinesthetic learners.

Cons: Limited in scope for older or more advanced learners; less focus on speaking and writing.

10. Flipped Classroom

Overview: A modern teaching method where traditional homework and classroom activities are reversed. Students first engage with content at home (via videos or readings) and then practice in class.

Focus: Active learning and practical application of language skills.

Characteristics:

Students learn new material outside of class (e.g., through video lessons or reading), and class time is used for discussion, projects, and problem-solving.

Students take greater responsibility for their learning.

Teachers act more as facilitators than traditional instructors.

Pros: More interaction and hands-on learning in the classroom; allows for personalized learning.

Cons: Relies on students' motivation and access to technology.

Conclusion

The best method for teaching English depends on the specific needs of the students, their level of proficiency, and the educational context. Many modern classrooms incorporate elements from multiple methods, such as CLT, TBLT, and the flipped classroom, to create an engaging, flexible learning environment. The trend today is to focus on communicative competence (using language for real-world interaction) while also balancing grammar instruction, vocabulary development, and pronunciation.

The list of used literature:

1. "Techniques and Principles in Language Teaching" by Diane Larsen-Freeman & Marti Anderson
2. "The Practice of English Language Teaching" by Jeremy Harmer
3. "Approaches and Methods in Language Teaching" by Jack C. Richards & Theodore S. Rodgers
4. "Second Language Acquisition and Second Language Learning" by Stephen D. Krashen

5. "Teaching by Principles: An Interactive Approach to Language Pedagogy"
by H. Douglas Brown

6. "The Cambridge Guide to Teaching English to Speakers of Other Languages" edited by Ronald Carter & David Nunan

7. "How to Teach English" by Jeremy Harmer

8. "The Lexical Approach: The State of ELT and a Way Forward" by Michael Lewis

9. "Methods that Work: Ideas for Literacy and Language Teachers" by Patricia M. Cunningham & Dorothy P. Hall

10. "The Silent Way: A New Approach to Language Teaching" by Caleb Gattegno